

#@APP-FORM-HEMSCAPF@#

Part B-1

1. Excellence #@REL-EVA-RE@#

1.1 Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives (and the extent to which they are ambitious and go beyond the state of the art) #@QUA-LIT-QL@#

In the face of escalating climate change impacts, **catalyzing a widespread shift towards pro-environmental behavior** stands as one of the formidable challenges of our generation. Motivating individuals to adopt pro-environmental and energy-efficient behaviors for greenhouse gas emission reduction remains a complex challenge within environmental psychology, even with many individuals already holding pro-environmental values¹. **Addressing this challenge necessitates transcending traditional intervention methods**, as evidenced by the limited success of approaches such as information dissemination, tailored education, feedback mechanisms, and social marketing¹. Prior work has shown several barriers to adopting energy-efficient measures for such motivated individuals, including economic considerations, difficulty implementing, limited knowledge or skills and knowledge acquisition requiring too much cognitive load². The contextual intricacies of barriers across diverse target audiences underline **the need for adaptable and individualized intervention strategies**³. Recent global events like the Corona pandemic and Ukraine war underscore society's capability to alter consumption patterns⁴, and thus prompt exploration into innovative approaches that can effectively address the multifaceted barriers to pro-environmental behavior change.

The recent emergence of **advanced conversational AI platforms** built over large language models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, Bard, and Perplexity AI, has sparked global research interest⁵. It is in this context that the ADVANCE project emerges, envisioning conversational agents (CAs, here defined as dialogue systems rooted in natural language processing (NLP) that respond to human inputs using human language) as potential facilitators for easy-to-use, customizable, cost-effective, and adaptable interventions. Tackling the limitations of state-of-the-art informational feedback approaches¹, the primary goal of my research is to explore the feasibility of utilizing CAs to provide proactive support to already pro-environmentally motivated individuals, aiding them in adopting energy-efficient behaviors. From this overarching aim, my research objectives emerge as follows:

[O1] Assess effectiveness of CAs to facilitate energy-efficient behavioral changes. While existing evidence hints at CAs' ability to support individuals' behavior change decisions, especially in the healthcare and physical activity contexts⁶ and attitude changes towards policy decisions⁷, the efficacy, feasibility and acceptability vary across studies and causal conclusions are lacking. I go beyond the state of the art by introducing CAs in the context of *sustainable* behavior change. My research will provide *first causal evidence* from an experimental study of the potential and effectiveness to enable energy-efficient behaviors, contributing to these agents' broader utility.

[O2] Investigate the mechanisms by which CAs facilitate human decision-making for adopting energy-efficient behaviors. While economic barriers can impede expensive and difficult-to-implement changes (renovations and installations), misperceptions or confusion about benefits and limited knowledge hinder smaller-scale adoptions⁸. Coupled with cognitive resource constraints, this can induce feelings of demotivation and helplessness, stemming from a perceived lack of control and viable options⁹. Research examining the role of conversational agents in shaping human decision-making processes is in its infancy^{6,10}. With a theory-driven approach, I will go beyond the state of the art, and illuminate the cognitive and affective mechanisms through which CAs support human choices to overcome aforementioned barriers by designing a conceptual framework rooted in the *self-determination theory* (SDT)'s main concepts of *competence*, *relatedness*, and *autonomy*¹¹, which have been shown to positively affect motivation and behavior change¹². This understanding will facilitate application of my findings by policymakers, grassroots initiatives, and leaders in energy and AI industries, and empower my career goal to work in research institutions at the intersection of AI services & sustainability science.

¹Rau et al, 2022, *Front Psychol* 13: 901927. ²Cattaneo, 2019, *Energy Effic* 12: 1293–1311. ³Byerly et al, 2018, *Front Ecol Environ* 16: 159–68. ⁴Appunn et al, 2023; Hartz & Lenck, 2023. ⁵van Dis et al, 2023, *Nature* 614: 224–26. ⁶Singh et al, 2023, *Npj Digit Med* 6: 1–10; Aggarwal et al, 2023, *J Med Internet Res* 25: e40789. ⁷Altay et al, 2023, *J Exp Psychol Appl* 29: 52–62; Zarouali et al, 2021, *Eur J Commun* 36: 53–68; Sohail et al, 2023, *Ann Biomed Eng*. ⁸Li et al, 2021, *Energy Res Soc Sci* 80: 102211. ⁹Christie et al, 2011, *Build Res Inf* 39: 450–58. ¹⁰Krügel et al, 2023, *Sci Rep* 13: 4569. ¹¹Ryan & Deci, 2000, *Am Psychol* 55: 68–78. ¹²Webb et al, 2013, *J Environ Psychol* 35: 59–66.

[O3] Develop a practical toolbox of recommendations for sustainability & energy policymakers.

Informed by my findings, I will compile a comprehensive toolbox of recommendations tailored for sustainability energy specialists and policymakers. For optimal deployment of CAs to promote pro-environmental behaviors, the toolbox will be structured towards users' Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation, as proposed in the COM-B model of behavior change¹³. Going beyond state of the art, recommendations will be tailored to quantified differences in demographics, socio-behavioral factors, and household types, to maximize effectiveness in diverse contexts¹⁴. This tangible outcome, shared with potential employers or collaborators, highlights my ability to generate practical solutions for complex issues, making me a valuable asset in interdisciplinary fields, enhancing my employability.

1.2 Soundness of the proposed methodology

Longitudinal randomized controlled experiment design. I will carry out a multi-wave online survey with an experimental design. Participants will be randomized into three distinct groups: (i) a *control group* receiving basic appeals to adopt energy-efficient behaviors, (ii) a *traditional information group* receiving informational flyers on online resources, and (iii) a *conversational agent group* which will engage with a CA (ChatGPT, Perplexity.ai) to learn methods for adopting energy-efficient behaviors. Interventions will target four energy-efficiency behaviors (Fig. 2), chosen based on the criteria cost-effectiveness, impact potential, and CA reliability, i.e., they are affordable, easily implementable, and have substantial impact when widely adopted. We pre-tested them with the CA Perplexity to ensure that effective, evidence-based communication on these behaviors would be within the CAs' capabilities.

<p>Adaptive thermostats 50-500€</p> <p>smart or programmable</p>			
<p>Energy reduction (mixed) thermostat -1°C=7% heat coldwashing=2-8% electric LED usage > 75% electric</p>	<p>Energy reduction (heat) thermostat reduction of 0.5 to 3°C = 3-25% heat energy</p>	<p>Energy reduction (heat) stoppers: -15% heat loss curtains: -40% heat loss</p>	<p>Energy reduction (heat) usage, away-times=8-30%</p>

Figure 2. Overview of energy-efficiency behaviors targeted in interventions.¹⁵

Implementation & data collection. I will collaborate with a survey panel provider (e.g., Bilendi), to recruit participants from two European countries: Germany (N=900) and Finland (N=300). These countries were selected due to differences in belief regarding individual efficacy and the effectiveness of informational interventions¹⁶. Both countries exhibit moderate pro-environmental beliefs, with Finnish households consuming more electricity¹⁷. Over a 5-month period, participants will be surveyed at monthly intervals, allowing for the collection of quantifiable data on the CA intervention's effectiveness in driving behavior change, measuring longer-term impact. I plan 6 survey waves, beginning with a baseline measurement (T0) assessing pro-environmental attitudes, cognitive abilities, and previous energy efficiency experience. Participants will receive their initial appeal to adopt energy-efficient behaviors, focusing on actions with minimal cost. Subsequent surveys (T1-T4) will appeal for changes on the energy efficiency behaviors from Fig 2 and measure their adoption and heating and electricity use reduction. Wherever possible, participants will be asked to provide anonymized evidence for behavioral changes (bills, receipts). A follow-up survey at T5 will capture positive spillovers and rebounds¹⁷ (e.g., preparation of renovations, water usage) and assess participants' CA usage over the past year. Participants in the conversational agent group will be instructed to share their chat protocols. **Ethics implications** will be considered all throughout this process. Guidelines by the Aalto University Research Ethics Committee will provide the framework here: all steps will be accompanied by consent practices and forms, including Letters of Information, and in-depth debriefing (see Form B-2).

Frameworks and analyses. A foundational part of my research methodology, I will adopt the Theory of Change (ToC) framework¹⁸, which is successfully employed in major organizations, international NGOs and even the UN, to outline the causal pathways through which CAs can facilitate energy-efficiency behavior. The ToC framework will help identify necessary prerequisites, interventions, and

¹³Michie et al, 2011, *Implement Sci* 6. ¹⁴Abrahamse et al, 2007, *J Environ Psychol* 27: 265–76. ¹⁵WWF, 2023; Energy Saving Trust, 2023; Energygov, 2023.¹⁶Mikuła et al, 2021, *Energies* 14: 5689. ¹⁷Urban & Kaiser, 2022, *Front Psychol* 13: 875419. ¹⁷Maki et al, 2019, *Nat Sustain* 2: 307–15. ¹⁸McLellan, 2021, *Soc Stud Sci* 51: 100–120.

expected outcomes for achieving the desired behavioral changes. This structured approach will enable systematic planning, monitoring, and evaluation of progress toward my research objectives.

For the analysis of both experimental and survey data, a pivotal component of my research, I will employ suitable statistical methods, i.e., linear regression models, analysis of variance, structural equation models, and descriptive statistics. These methods will allow me to assess the impact of the CA intervention on participants' behavior change outcomes [O1]. I will contribute a new comprehensive theoretical framework based on *SDT*, which suggests that addressing competence, relatedness, and autonomy needs enhances motivation toward positive outcomes [O2]. The framework will help understand whether CA interaction (1) fosters *competence* by targeting misperceptions and provides valuable knowledge and skills; (2) whether it bolsters *relatedness* by offering fun, interactive experiences, counteracting motivational deficits; (3) and whether CAs empower *autonomy* by offering choices and alternatives, potentially reducing feelings of helplessness and increasing openness to larger behavior changes through self-efficacy gains by experiencing small-scale successes first. I will, for this purpose, *improve my understanding* of how to **exploit the rich potential of data derived from CA transcripts and open-text responses**, via a semi-automated approach to code and categorize the available texts, creating robust frameworks for analyzing factors such as sophistication and quality of interactions with CAs and positive or negative sentiment, and content-specific patterns in open-text responses. From the computational expertise in ██████████'s group and Aalto's CS department *I will learn* to develop **algorithmic solutions for performing automated content analysis using state-of-the-art natural language processing (NLP) techniques**. *I will learn* how to appropriately annotate a small set of CA transcripts and open text responses and how to use them to design supervised models or fine-tune pretrained models. Based on these analyses, led by the COM-B model, I will map findings onto capability, opportunity and motivation barriers of distinct subgroups and individualized contexts.

Integration of methods and disciplines is crucial for my research objectives, which encompass complex human behaviors influenced by psychological, and technological factors. I will integrate methods from psychology and *novel-to-me methods from computer science* supported by ██████████'s lab, *to learn to construct a more comprehensive understanding* of multifaceted processes behind energy-efficient behaviors. Combining statistical methods from psychology with appropriate algorithms and NLP techniques from computer science *will equip me with the rare and cutting-edge knowledge to derive comprehensive insights from a wide range of sources*, i.e. from survey responses, conversational agent transcripts, and open-text answers.

Gender dimension and other diversity aspects. I will ensure an equal representation sample (gender, but also age and education), including the option to express diverse gender identities. My analyses will account for gender-related pro-environmental behavior disparities¹⁹ and factors that I have identified to impact CA usage²⁰. I will incorporate voluntary items to address intersectionality with such diversity aspects such as ethnicity (including refugees), social class and sexual orientation, and assess potential barriers faced by these minority groups, guaranteeing representativeness and inclusivity.

AI dimension. AI plays a dual role in my project: one, I evaluate suitability and effectiveness of generative CAs in promoting pro-environmental behavior. Two, I will learn how to leverage NLP, a branch of AI, to analyze research data, including CA interaction transcripts and open-text responses. Ensuring robustness in both cases is paramount. For the former, a feasibility study with the chosen CA guarantees technical robustness. Pre-tested conversational guidelines will meticulously consider concerns regarding hallucination, trustworthiness, and informed consent. To minimize participant impact, detailed information on CAs built over LLMs will be provided in curated information materials. Quantitative and qualitative measures will assess CA response quality, including intricacy, correctness, and expert evaluation. Social robustness will be weighed by considering operational context and environment. Rigorous validation and benchmarking of NLP models using expert-labeled data will ensure the reliability of my analytical methods.

Open science practices, research data management and management of other research outputs.

I prioritize **transparency, reproducibility, reuse and accessibility** in my research to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange within the scientific community. I'll **pre-register** publications

¹⁹Kennedy & Kmec, 2018, *Environ Sociol* 4: 299–310. ²⁰Kacperski et al, 2023.

on the Open Science Framework (OSF) when possible and **publish open access** for broad access. Pre-prints will be shared on OSF-based repositories like ArXiv, and I'll actively participate in open peer-reviewed processes. Results will be shared with participants, their concerns will be discussed. Our research data will be handled in strict accordance with **Aalto's data safety and protection guidelines**, ensuring registration, communication, and compliance with GDPR. Given the sensitive nature of the data, it will be securely stored on Aalto servers and accessible only to research group members via VPN file transfer. On completion of the project, **aggregated data, codebooks and analysis scripts** will be shared on OSF with PIDs/DOIs. Data will be in interoperable .csv/.Rdata formats and scripts in .R format, accompanied by comprehensive metadata and Creative Commons license to facilitate reuse.

1.3 *Quality of the supervision, training and of the two-way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host*

Prof. [REDACTED] is an accomplished researcher (h-index of 13 and >1000 citations) and Tenure [REDACTED]y, where she collaborates with 6 senior experts ([REDACTED]) as well as other early career researchers on human-computer interaction, studying experiences among human, artificial and non-human entities. She is the best person to supervise ADVANCE due to her vast experience in merging methodologies from computational and social science, as she is a world-renowned expert on utilizing digital behavioral data to study our internet-mediated lives, combining passively collected web browsing traces with online surveys and experiments. She holds publications in top journals and conferences such as Information Retrieval, CSCW and AAI ICWSM. She has an impressive track record of securing international research grants and leading multidisciplinary teams on research projects funded by grants totaling over 1.8M Euros (657K as Lead-PI, 1.22M as Co-PI). She has demonstrated remarkable leadership and supervisory skills far surpassing her academic age, including supervising 13 master theses, one doctoral researcher and two postdoctoral researchers, including myself. Our in the last year established mentorship (through her [REDACTED] project at the [REDACTED]), though geographically remote, has already produced a preprint about ChatGPT usage under review²⁰ and lays the foundation for a successful and fruitful collaboration. She will be pivotal in propelling me towards the realization of my career aspirations, also due to her extensive multidisciplinary and international research collaboration network from, for example, Bern and Zurich University, the Indian Institute of Technology, GESIS, and the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence, which will bolster the visibility of my project and bring in insights from varied cultural and discipline backgrounds.

My supervision will be supported by Dr. [REDACTED] Unit Director [REDACTED] at [REDACTED] and Docent of Environmental Policy ([REDACTED]), an expert on sustainability transformations and behavioral science (>150 publications, h-index 30, >2400 citations). She has extensive supervisory experience (8 PhDs) and has received funding for 15 research and development projects covering European and national funding instruments. She will guide the project on knowledge use in planning and decision-making and provide insights from the fields of behavioral change, social learning, and sustainability agency.

Other members of my academic advisory board will be [REDACTED] (Prof. of Survey Research, [REDACTED]) and [REDACTED] (Prof. of Behavioral Public Policy, [REDACTED]).

Planned training activities for researcher

My supervisor and I have defined a **research and methods training plan and will define a career development plan throughout the course of the project (WP5)**, which includes weekly internals with [REDACTED] and her lab, fully integrating me into her department. Monthly internals involving Dr. [REDACTED] will enhance the research design phase (WP1). During the CA intervention design (Task 1.2) and data analysis phase (WP3), bi-weekly sessions with experts in the CS department on NLP and LLM methods will enhance the rigorousness of my analyses. For WP4, **Training for key transferable skills** will be provided by Aalto's Research Data Management Network, and their biannual webinar series where I will gain novel insights into research integrity and Open Science practices. I will take part in the Business Finland's Research to Business program, supported by the university's innovation services, to bolster my **innovation and entrepreneurship skills** (IP questions and commercialization),

including contacting external testing partners such as energy companies and grassroots environmental initiatives for exploitation. I will take the opportunity of Aalto's staff training in **communication and public engagement** and in **leadership, teamwork, and adaptability**. Finally, I will take inspiration from previous successful **citizen science projects** within Aalto (such as outreach in Heureka Science Center), and apply for funding to implement such projects, pending applicable results. I will train with HR administrative support at the time of joining, as their grant and budgeting support will help me (1) **manage existing funding and apply for further funding**, and (2) with **data management, research ethics and legal consultation** for projects.

Two-way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and host organization

Aligned with the values and mission statement of my supervisors, the CS department, and Aalto University, two-way knowledge transfer will occur on 3 dimensions: **Teaching, Research and Networking**. **In terms of teaching**, my results will feed into educational content at Aalto, and I will enhance students' learning experience by sharing my international, inter-sectoral and interdisciplinary experiences and content to courses and workshops. My expansive data collection will allow for novel research questions tackled in Bachelor and Master theses, which will enhance my own findings and increase publication numbers; internal funding opportunities will allow us to hire research assistants that will gain insights into interdisciplinary and academic processes, strengthening my leadership and supervision abilities. **In terms of research**, ADVANCE is strongly aligned with Aalto's main value statements, sustainability and interdisciplinarity. A feedback loop is in place, where my cutting-edge research contributes to Aalto's global attractiveness, visibility, and reputation, and I receive opportunities for conducting independent research mentored by experts in their respective fields, e.g., from the CS lab and the Engineering Psychology Lab. Support for further grant applications will sustain my ideas beyond the termination of the project, while bringing in financing for Aalto's mission to reach important sustainability goals. My expertise in design of field experiments across a variety of technology-heavy topics will be further expanded through training-through-research, collaboration sessions such as brown-bags, and intra-university knowledge exchanges, to improve on my methodological skills of effective use of NLP. Here, I can contribute cross-disciplinary insights. **In terms of networking**, I will share my experience working on large-scale applied Horizon 2020 projects with fellow colleagues and their networks to help integrate Aalto into future consortia that might benefit from Aalto's research strengths. Aalto's innovation services will advance my networking opportunities with research institutes in Finland (HELSUS, FCAI) and [REDACTED]'s international network (with researchers from Universities in Amsterdam, Poznan in Poland, Zurich and Bern in Switzerland, and India, to just name a few) will give me access to research and mobility opportunities. I can share with new colleagues my connections with such actors as [REDACTED], [REDACTED], [REDACTED], [REDACTED], [REDACTED]. Aalto will additionally provide me with opportunities for media coverage and media training, and kickstart collaborations with non-academic and grassroots organizations on environmental issues that can benefit from my results (Finnish Fridays for Future).

In summary, I will gain transferable skills and competences, especially in data science and NLP methods, improving my career prospects and employability at such organizations as such as the MPI, IPCC or ICF. Finally, as a female-presenting, non-binary and LGBTQI* early-career researcher I will in turn support Aalto's mission of increasing minority representation in computer science, encouraging more minority researchers to work on climate research in computer science related fields. Receiving the MSCA will aid in improving Aalto's and my own alignment with principles of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.

1.4 Quality and appropriateness of researcher's professional experience, competences, skills

During my PhD and after, I have conducted **applied social and environmental psychology research**, resulting in **24 publications** (11 first-author, h-index 8). I have worked in **2 Horizon projects** ([REDACTED]) and received 2 further **Horizon 2020 grants as Co-PI** ([REDACTED]). I have achieved numerous research accolades and scholarships, including the [REDACTED] **for best MSc thesis**, the **Vanier Scholarship** (most prestigious PhD research award in Canada), the Western Research Grant, the Western Graduate Research Scholarship, the Mitacs Globalink Research Award

and various smaller awards, **totaling over 200,000\$ in funding**. I have presented my research at over **20 conferences**, receiving various attendance scholarships such as for the Dark Sky Meeting at Oxford in 2023. My research is at the intersection of **novel technologies and sustainable, pro-environmental behaviors**. I have implemented models and incentives for more energy-efficient electric vehicle charging (in **Energy Policy, JEP**), studied the ambivalence and paths to acceptance of connected, autonomous vehicles (in **TR:F, HCI**), and conducted field research on collective energy actions, testing interventions for improved participation and uptake of energy-efficiency behaviors through social identity and group process interventions (in **ERSS**). Parallel to my field research, I have participated in papers on the **algorithmic bias**, with implications for **gender equality** and **news consumption** (both in **NM&S**). I have under review one paper on **citizens' interaction with CAs** from my current position at the [REDACTED] where I am gaining first insights into how individuals interact with AI-powered services, a large asset for this MSCA. These factors make me a prime candidate to conduct first large-scale experimental research on the use of CAs support energy-efficiency behaviors.

2. Impact #@IMP-ACT-IA@#

2.1 Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of the researcher and contribution to his/her skills development

Specific measures to enhance career perspectives and employability of the researcher inside and/or outside academia

I will be supported by Prof. [REDACTED] and the Aalto CS department, as well as my secondary supervisor [REDACTED] to take the next step in my desired career as a researcher at a science institution or think tank for climate and sustainability research (such as the New Institute, PIK, MPI, ICF or HELSUS), by expanding my research, engagement and impact portfolio, becoming more competitive for permanent positions, while supporting potential future aspirations for tenure-track positions. My mid-term goal, following **career development plans** that will be designed with Dr. [REDACTED], is to lead a research group to replicate my findings on CAs across other contexts and geographical points, establishing a new research field combining CAs and sustainable behavior change.

Research Excellence. Funding, equipment and facilities (from Aalto Data Hub, Science-IT) will help me produce high-quality research. This includes writing support for publications, deliverables, and policy guidelines. My supervisors cover between them mentoring and training in areas of data science, and experimental behavioral research design with a focus on sustainability transformations. Of particular impact will be supervision and training resources available at the CS department for training me in natural language processing and computational social science methods, which will integrate perfectly with my prior data science knowledge in more traditional statistical analysis methods. Finally, research in two countries as distinct as Finland and Germany enables a cross-cultural perspective on the research that is unique to this opportunity, supported by both my supervisors' international profile.

Networking and Collaboration will be facilitated with research institutes (HELSUS, SYKE), industry partners (through Industrial Internet Campus and Aalto Factory of the Future, see also their collaborations with Nokia, ABB), and other universities (Helsinki U), to aid build my professional network, learn about new research trends and techniques, and collaborate on interdisciplinary research projects, with the help of the Aalto Networking Platform. This includes contact with Aalto's Scientific and Artistic Advisory Board; collaboration with the Finnish Center for Artificial Intelligence, a community of experts that brings together top talents in academia, industry and the public sector to solve real-life problems using both existing and novel AI; and events such as the Helsinki Distinguished Lecture Series, AIX Forum, and the Multidisciplinary Seminar Series, which are all meeting places for individuals applying AI in different domains and developing new AI tools and methods.

Career Development and Training will be provided in leadership, project management, communication, and entrepreneurship, as well as career counseling and job search support, for which Aalto has established the Harald Herlin Learning Centre. Aalto specifically offers My Dialogue for Academics to help researchers set goals and plan their work, and Personal Impact, a series with courses such as Leading as Practice, Thinking Tools and Mind & Study, and personalized information skills training with Meet an Information Specialist, which I plan to utilize to develop my career options.

Expected contribution of proposed skills development to the future career of the researcher.

ADVANCE will contribute to my development on 3 dimensions, which are aligned with and summarized based the Eurodoc skills report: 1) **Academic skills** (including cognitive, research and digital skills), 2) **Leadership skills** (including communication, interpersonal, supervision and mobility) and 3) **Professional skills** (including career development and enterprise skills).

Academic skills: I will advance my knowledge on rigorous study design to produce high-quality research outputs, specifically the implementation of a multi-disciplinary/multi-context longitudinal study; here I will learn most from [REDACTED], an expert in behavior science implementations. Supervision from I [REDACTED] and the CS department will enhance my use of tools and techniques for analysis and interpretation of complex data, including advanced computational and statistical methods for data analysis of large-scale conversational data (NLP methods). Collaborating with two supervisors, both experts in their fields, will cultivate critical integrative thinking skills and innovative solutions combining computer science and sustainability.

Leadership skills: I will strengthen my ability to work in interdisciplinary teams, and to contribute to projects that require very diverse sets of expertise and perspectives. This also includes overcoming challenges of intercultural communication and improving my intersectoral awareness, especially when supervising students at various stages of learning.

Professional skills: Entering a new field will improve my skills of gap identification and development, require adaptability and openness to learning new concepts, tools, and methodologies, especially when keeping up with emerging trends in the enterprising field of AI-powered services. Aalto in particular, leader in the provision of incubator and accelerator services and business support, will help me disseminate my recommendation toolbox, and understand which insights from my research will enhance collaborations with entrepreneurial ventures. This will lead to better exploitation of innovation ideas that will evolve from this project, which can be adopted by industry and policymakers.

2.2 Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities

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Plan for dissemination and exploitation activities, including communication activities (WP4):

The following section covers the three main areas of activities (**scientific, public, industry**) I will carry out to engage interested parties with my results and outputs. The goal is to promote pro-environmental behavior change, affect policy decisions, and advance the field of AI-powered applications.

Scientific Activities (Dissemination and Exploitation). Target audience: researchers, academics and experts in the field of social, applied and environmental psychology and behavioral science, sustainability science, and computational social science, including human-machine interaction. The ADVANCE recommendation toolbox will be disseminated through contacts with think tanks and research institutions and exploited by experts in the field of AI-services and HCI, as well as political science experts on sustainability and pro-environmental behavior. I will publish a minimum of 2 scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals of high impact in my field (e.g., *Nature: Human Behavior*, *Computers in Human Behavior*). I will disseminate my findings in at least 2 academic conferences (such as ICEP, IC2S2), and 1 symposium (FCA's AI Day), fostering discussions and exchanging insights with fellow researchers and academics. After project completion, I will collaborate with researchers interested in my open access datasets and scripts.

Public Activities (Dissemination and Communication). Target audience: general public, groups with strong pro-environmental motivations and values. I will provide a project website, explaining my research in lay terms, including some easy-to-understand infographics with results of my research. The website will host the ADVANCE recommendation toolbox. Supported by Aalto's marketing team, and based on experience from Horizon projects on cutting-edge tech such as autonomous vehicles, I expect considerable media interest, so I will contribute to 2 press releases and engage in media outreach to raise awareness about the potential of CAs in energy efficiency, if results support this. After entering the survey at T0, panel participants will have the opportunity to sign up to a webinar with me to discuss their concerns and expectations of conversing with CAs. If results support positive outcomes, I will

contact and collaborate with environmental groups such as Fridays for Future to align my findings with their campaigns for sustainable living, continuing this past the project ending.

Industry Activities (Dissemination and Exploitation). Target audience: energy providers, technology developers and policy makers. I will generate a concise policy brief, highlighting policy implications of my research, and distribute it in at least one AI industry conference (e.g., European Chatbot & Conversational AI Summit) to engage with professionals about the potential of CAs in the energy-efficiency field. Through Aalto's industry support network and AI hubs, I will network with CA technology developers to enhance my findings with their insights, while disseminating my results to enhance the effectiveness of their products. Pending positive results, I will engage with energy providers in Germany (e.g., Stadtwerke) to integrate CAs into their customer engagement strategies, promoting energy-efficient choices. Pending results, I will explore possibilities for commercial products/services based on research outcomes, targeting companies in energy and technology sectors.

Strategy for the management of intellectual property, foreseen protection measures

The main output of the project will be scientific publications and the ADVANCE recommendation toolbox. Scientific publications will be published under creative commons licenses and openly accessible for all. I also intend to make the toolbox publicly available and usable, and will consult Aalto legal services and the intellectual property guide for optimal implementation once finalized.

2.3. The magnitude and importance of the project's contribution to the expected scientific, societal and economic impacts

Practicing a sustainable way of life is important to 80% of the German and Finnish population, with 20% highly reporting being highly motivated²¹. But many face barriers when translating this motivation into action. Reaching this population will have clear **environmental and economic impacts**. In Germany, the average yearly heating energy is 13.5 MWh and cost per household is around 900 Euros²². Disseminated by policy institutes and energy providers, reaching even a small percentage (5%) of a pro-environmentally motivated group would have widespread impact: reduction of energy consumption by a conservative 10% (see the 5-20% projected possible savings from our interventions), this would translate to energy savings of 5 Mio MWh and 90 Euro a year per household, important cost savings particularly for lower SES households, for whom main barriers might be lack of knowledge and self-efficacy. For Finnish residents, environmental impact would be even higher, as the annual household heat energy consumption is 18 MWh. Furthermore, ADVANCE raises consumer awareness about energy consumption patterns and transformative impact of even small behavioral changes on the environment, which can lead to positive spillovers if the pathways towards behavior change used by CAs affect competence and autonomy self-perceptions. Such impacts have not so far been achieved by any informational interventions in the household energy-efficiency field, so I lay the foundation to answer whether such savings can be possible at individual level. In the future, nation-wide levels could be achievable, as the cost of implementing CAs is decreasing, and individualized, privacy-conscious and specialized implementations of CAs are being developed. My results might prospect development of cutting-edge products and services that seamlessly integrate CAs to encourage energy-efficient behavior change, which aligns with the growing demand for sustainable solutions.

In terms of societal impact, as CAs are widely applicable, public and NGO organizations and even institutions such as universities can benefit by providing curated CAs in special contexts such as social housing projects, energy communities, and energy islands, and empower community organization, which has been shown to have much higher impact in localized areas²³. At the policy level, my research outcomes will inform decision-making processes related to energy efficiency and responsible AI utilization. I aim to provide guidelines to influence the establishment of industry standards, ensuring responsible and effective deployment of AI-driven behavior change interventions.

Finally, in terms of scientific impact, with at least 2 planned high-impact publications, I will make significant contributions to the scientific landscape by for the first time investigating the intricate relationship of large-language-model technology, environmental psychology, and energy-efficiency,

²¹European Commission & Kantar, 2023. ²²Destatis, 2023; Statista, 2022. ²³Daryanto & Song, 2021, *J Business Res.* 123: 208–219. spawning a novel research area. My study will facilitate cross-disciplinary collaboration, potentially resulting in the development of innovative NLP methods for assessing CA effectiveness promoting deeper understanding of behavior change mechanisms and insights into the potential, far-reaching impact of CAs in the field of environmental science.

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3. Quality and Efficiency of the Implementation #@QUA-LIT-QL@# #@WRK-PLA-WP@#
 #@CON-SOR-CS@# #@PRJ-MGT-PM@#

3.1 Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages

The planned project duration is 24 months, with the 1st quarter dedicated to experimental definition, and set-up of dissemination, training and management activities. In the 2nd quarter I will carry out data collection and first data related trainings. In the 3rd quarter, I will conduct data analysis and interpretation. In the 4th quarter I will complete the follow-up data collection and wrap up dissemination. Throughout ADVANCE, dissemination and exploitation will be accompanied by training activities as outlined in 1.3 and 2.1. All Milestones (MS) and Deliverables (D) are listed below.

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
WP1:Experimental definition					MS2													MS8						
Task 1.1. Experimental design and survey item selection																								
Task 1.2. Chat setup, testing and intervention design																								
WP2:Data collection											MS4									MS10				
WP3:Data analysis& interpretation																MS7						MS11		
WP4:Dissemination, exploitation				D1	MS3				D2				D3			D4	MS9		D5		D6	D7	D8	
WP5:Training and management		MS1										MS5	MS6										MS12	MS13

Table 1. Gantt with Milestones (MS) and Deliverables (D) in chronological order, details below.

Milestones

- MS1: Training plan finalization
- MS2+MS8: Final exp. definition & materials
- MS3+MS9: Preregistration of design in OSF
- MS4: Surveys T0-T4 complete
- MS5: Preliminary career development plan
- MS6: Annual progress report
- MS7: Preliminary data processing complete
- MS10: Survey T5 complete
- MS11: Integration of follow-up data complete
- MS12: Final career development plan
- MS13: Final progress report

Deliverables

- D1: Website online, project introduction blog post
- D2: Conference submission (ICEP), blog post
- D3: Conference submission (IC2S2), blog post
- D4: Scientific paper submission, upload to ArXiv, accompanying press release + blog post
- D5: AI industry conference participation, blog post
- D6: Symposium presentation, blog post
- D7: Recommendation toolbox
- D8: Scientific paper submission, upload to ArXiv, accompanying press release + blog post

[WP1] Experimental definition. (M1-M18, Supervision: ██████████) **Task 1.1.** will tackle experimental design and survey item selection. Design planning will be conducted following the *ToC* framework. I will use scientifically validated scales from research on Self-Determination Theory, AI literacy and pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors. **Task 1.2.** will tackle chat setup and evaluation, including in-depth feasibility studies to fine-tune the intervention design. I will code the experiment, hosted on SoSci Survey, a German-based scientific survey platform. Intervention materials such as online resources for the flyers and CA guidelines will be prepared. The ethics committee will be consulted for input on all design steps. **Milestones MS2 and MS8** at months 5 and 18 will be met by finalization of experimental design and set-up of surveys.

[WP2]: Data collection. (M6-M20, Supervision: ██████████). I will set-up, organize, carry out and follow through on data collection with a survey panel provider, to obtain N=900 German and N=300 Finnish participants at T4. Over 4 months, they will report repeatedly on their energy-efficiency behaviors, randomized into experimental groups (CA conversations vs. control group of no intervention vs. a traditional method of flyers with online resources). At T5, I will re-contact participants for a short follow-up survey to study spillovers and longer-term effects. **Milestones MS4 and MS10** at months 11 and 20 will be met by finalization of data collection.

[WP3]: Data analysis and interpretation. (M9-M22, Supervision: ██████████). Data analysis strategies will be designed and carried out, using traditional quantitative multi-group comparisons (LMs, SEMs), and a special focus on novel, mixed-method and NLP approaches for CA interactions. **Milestone MS7** at month 16 will complete data processing of the main survey, and **MS11** at month 22 will complete integration of follow-up data as well as finalize data interpretation.

[WP4]: Dissemination, exploitation. (M5-M24, Supervision: ██████████). Scientific, policy and industry contexts will be tackled. I will set up the website (**D1**). Throughout the project, I will meet with interested participants and stakeholders, present at both academic (**D2, D3**) and industry conferences and small-group meetings (**D5, D6**), publish press releases and blog posts on the website, and publish the ADVANCE toolbox for exploitation by interested parties (**D7**). Scientific publication is a long-term process, which will span the entirety of WP4, but I will follow open-science principles to archive preprints of publications at the time of submission (**D4, D8**). **Milestones MS3 and MS9** at months 5 and 18 will consist of preregistrations of our research design and hypotheses on OSF.

[WP5]: Training and management. (M9-M22, Supervision: ██████████). At M2, the training data plan will be completed (**MS1**). Across the project, skill trainings will be carried out, including internal team meetings, specialized data science and LLM methodology trainings, networking, collaboration, and leadership trainings. **Milestones MS5 and MS12** mark career development plan finalization, and **MS6 and MS13** mark progress reports to summarize learnings and outcomes.

Risk mitigation: Key risks for the project include: (i) *Participant recruitment difficulties:* The project may encounter higher attrition rates or fail to reach the desired participation rates. Mitigation strategies in the past have involved incentivizing participants with increased rates by the panel provider at their own cost to meet the promised rates; (ii) *CA quality issues:* CAs could provide hallucinations or false information. Mitigation strategies encompass rigorous feasibility tests for expected intervention behaviors shortly before deployment and adaptive approaches for behavior substitution if necessary; (iii) *Participant discomfort from CA interactions:* Participants may encounter negative experiences when interacting with the CA. Mitigation involves informed consent at the beginning of the study, continuous support during data collection periods, including webinars and Q&A sessions. The right to withdraw from the study will be emphasized at various stages.

3.2 *Quality and capacity of the host institutions and participating organisations, including hosting arrangements*

I will conduct the project within Aalto University's renowned Computer Science department, known for its top 10 ranking in Europe and top 100 globally. I will have access to leading researchers in project-relevant fields such as machine learning, data mining, and engineering psychology, fostering collaboration and consultation opportunities. I will access essential resources, including workspaces, IT equipment, high-performance computing, and data management support through the Science-IT project and the Triton HPC cluster, part of the Finnish Grid and Cloud Infrastructure (FGCI). Aalto provides exceptional support services, covering HR, grant writing, budgeting, data management, research ethics, legal counsel, IT support, pedagogical training, technology transfer and commercialization assistance, and work-life balance and mental health support. Prof. ██████████ will contribute initial seed funding alongside the MSCA funding for incidentals to support the longitudinal study design.

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